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Introduction

In the collection of materials of the conference, the role and role of Science, Education and production in the era of globalization, the pressing problems of the issues of interaction of these processes, feedback on their solutions were presented by mature specialists of the field.

In addition, research on the scientific and practical topic, carried out in the economics, Exact Sciences, Natural Sciences and socio-humanities during the globalization period, information is presented in the scientific and practical fields, which includes the latest innovative technologies in the fields of production.

It can be argued that this collection is one of the specific intersections of current thoughts and innovative ideas of the world of science. This scientific and practical conference was actively attended by professors and scientific researchers engaged in scientific research in Uzbekistan and foreign countries. In increasing the position of the scientific and practical conference, the professors and teachers of domestic and foreign higher educational institutions made a significant contribution.

Professors and teachers of foreign higher educational institutions who actively participated in the work of the conference made a worthy contribution to the high level of interaction with scientists of our country. The processes of international cooperation with foreign countries and exchange with them in the field of Science in the era of globalization have a positive effect on the development of Higher Education, the fields of Science and production. The materials of this conference are special in that they include a wide range of research, from theoretical developments to practical solutions, demonstrating the diversity of approaches and directions in this area.

In conclusion, it should be noted that this scientific and practical conference will be a very useful collection for everyone who is interested in modern research in the fields of further development of Higher Education, Science, Education and production in the era of globalization. The authors are responsible for the content and quality of the articles and abstracts included in the collection.

INSURANCE FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL BUSINESS AND PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract

By 2030, Uzbekistan set an ambitious goal to become an upper-middle-income nation, putting special emphasis on developing a sizable and stable middle-class socioeconomic stratum. The present reforms in Uzbekistan predominantly target the development of small enterprises and private entrepreneurship (SME) as SMEs have the greatest potential for creating a true base for forming a middle class. In addition to outlining the evidence for the SME's social and economic value, this article also addresses the current state of SME policy and its future prospects in Uzbekistan.

Keywords unemployment, entrepreneurship, economic value, infrastructure, SME.

Introduction

One-third of the population in Uzbekistan is under the age of 29, and half of the country's residents live in rural areas, making it the most densely populated nation in Central Asia. Job creation is a pressing and difficult goal because there are 800,000 persons under the age of 29 who enter the labor force every year.[1]

The development of private micro and small enterprises (MSEs) and entrepreneurship has repeatedly been stated as a priority by the Uzbek president now. Small businesses are now acknowledged to be a major contributor to economic growth, an increase in GDP, and the principal answer to pressing social issues like unemployment, poverty, especially among women and young people, and a low quality of life.

Small companies in Uzbekistan comprise individual entrepreneurs and micro and small enterprises.[2] Without taking into account a revenue component or the

ownership structure, the size of an enterprise is determined by the number of employees. By industry, different employee thresholds apply.

There really is no formal definition for medium - sized enterprises in the regulations. However to the proposed President Order,[3] the government wants to make revisions to legislation and broaden the scope of conditions required to qualify for being recognized as a small firm, commencing from 1 January 2019. According to draft suggestions, the following entities will be classed as small and medium-sized businesses.[4]

- individual businessperson;
- micro businesses having little more than 25 employees on average each year;
- small businesses having no more than 100 employees on average every year;
- medium-sized firms with an average yearly number of workers of not more than 250.

The amount and caliber of resources that may be used in the manufacturing process affect the chances for economic growth. For the objectives of the authors' research, the production process and resource provision of production are studied in the framework of territorial localization (region, municipality) (region, municipality). Defining the potential for the growth of entrepreneurship in the region entails determining the content and analyzing the resources of the relevant territory. At the same time, in addition to territorial binding, there are elements of resource provision in connection to the scale of production in the region (big, medium and small enterprises) (large, medium and small businesses). In this regard, the writers highlight the issue of identifying and analyzing those resources of the region that impact the growth of small and medium-sized companies (SMEs) in the region. In this area, research is not active enough. Considering the relevance of the problem in terms of contributing to the development of regions with SME potential, we deem it important to perform a research on this topic.

Results and discussions

As part of the resources of the resource potential of the region, the authors identified:

- organic (geological, climatic, mineral, and biological);
- human resources (human resources and their degree of qualification);
- production (results of economic activity of economic entities and the people of the region);
- financial (the amount of budget revenues, financial resources of firms and earnings of the inhabitants of the region) (the volume of budget revenues, financial resources of enterprises and incomes of the population of the region),

– infrastructural (condition of economic, industrial and social infrastructures of the region);

- innovative (parameters for the introduction of scientific and technology breakthroughs in the regional economy);

- the consumer (total purchasing power of the population of the region).

The variables (conditions) of the resource potential of the region include those that are the most managed and regulated and contribute to

the construction of the corporate environment, based on the aims specified by the topic of management:

- institutional (evolution of the regulatory framework, informal institutions for controlling enterprise) (development of the regulatory framework, informal institutions for regulating entrepreneurship),

- managerial (governmental support for entrepreneurship, the amount of managerial culture entrepreneurs) (state support for entrepreneurship, the level of managerial culture entrepreneurs).

As already established, small and medium-sized firms constitute a structural part of entrepreneurship. But because small and medium-sized enterprises operate differently, it's important to be clear about the resource's qualities, the possibilities above. The composition of its structural components determines the peculiarity of the resource potential for SMEs. Specific aspects (resources and factors) of the resource potential of the region for the growth of SMEs are:

- sectoral structure of the region's economy, which permits exploiting the competitive advantages of SMEs;

- creative processes in the development of technology, technology, organization of production, the formulation of the requirements of the people, which increase the available area of activity benefit for SMEs;

- specific measures of state assistance for SMEs.

Based on the above, it can be said that the main directions of proportional development of the regions of Uzbekistan in the medium-term perspective (2022-2026) are as follows:

- to improve the efficiency of the existing free economic zones, technical parks, small industrial zones, special logistics, pharmaceutical and tourism zones in the regions, while expanding their economic potential;

- expansion of the development potential of new service facilities for business entities focused on providing digital technology services (communication and information, IT-programming and electronic services) in the regions;

- introduction of energy and resource saving systems in regional industry, reduction of energy and resource use;

- the creation of new tourist goods based on currently unused resources for the continuous growth of domestic tourism in the regions will help reduce the impact of the coronavirus epidemic on the tourism industry;

- creation and development of new services (ecotourism, wellness, sports and recreation facilities) that use the natural resources and climate of rural areas; - establishment of services to the population based on the Internet (electronic order) in the regions;

Conclusion

It is necessary to develop laboratories, wholesale markets, and logistics centers that meet international standards and quality requirements in the regions in order to increase the volume of manufactured and marketed products, increase added value, expand the export geography, and diversify the economy. These measures provide a favorable opportunity to achieve higher economic performance and increase the possibility of inclusion in value added chains.

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